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Innovations in integrated agriculture in India

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Abstract

Integrated farming is one of the best farming techniques or practices developed in India and is now being promoted globally as an all-around development of agriculture, animal husbandry, and other vocations connected to fundamental agricultural practices. Integrated farming has the potential to make the agricultural sector lucrative, which has previously been demonstrated to be mostly a subsistence sector and a primary cause for quitting this age-old industry and migrating to cities. IFS is a farm enterprise that combines crop, livestock, aquaculture, poultry, sericulture, and agro-forestry to produce economic and sustainable agricultural output via resource efficiency. The IFS model is designed in such a way that waste created by one component becomes an input for another, resulting in the effective recycling of agricultural and animal wastes in the integrated system. Crop intensification and diversity result in increased yield per unit area. Aside from that, IFS aids in the control of insect pests, illnesses, and weeds through natural cropping system management, and less hazardous agrochemicals are used in agricultural production. This article aims to How integrated agriculture developed in India and its innovative ideas are thoroughly reviewed in this article.

Keywords: Agro-forestry, farming techniques, integrated farming, IFS, etc.

Introduction

Integrated farming is another farming approach or practice that originated in India and is now being promoted internationally as an all-around development of agriculture, animal husbandry, and other professions associated with basic agricultural practices. Integrated farming can make the agricultural sector profitable, which has previously been shown to be primarily a subsistence sector and a key reason for leaving this age-old industry and relocating to cities. IFS is a farm enterprise that integrates agriculture, livestock, aquaculture, poultry, sericulture, and agro-forestry to produce economically and sustainably. The IFS model is structured so that one component's waste becomes an input for another, resulting in the effective recycling of agricultural and animal wastes in the integrated system. Crop diversification and intensification result in higher yield per unit area. Aside from that, IFS helps control insect pests, diseases, and weeds through natural cropping system management, and less harmful agrochemicals are utilized in agricultural production.

Crops (field crops, horticultural crops), agroforestry (Agri-silviculture, Agri-horticulture, Agri-pastoral, Silvi-pastoral,

horti-pastoral), livestock (dairy, pigs, poultry, small ruminants), fisheries, mushroom, and bee culture are all integrated into the IFS model. In an IFS model, field crops are sown for food production. Horticultural and vegetable crops may also supply 2-3 times the energy of cereal crops, guaranteeing nutritional security as well as economic sustainability on the same piece of land. Following harvesting, crop wastes can be used as animal feed for dairy and goat production. Animal excreta can also be utilized as organic fertilizer or vermicomposting, increasing soil fertility and reducing the demand for synthetic fertilizers. Animal excreta, once again, can be dried, composted, or liquid composted to produce biogas and energy for residential use.

Materials and Methods

The study is based on secondary data gathered from various Articles, Websites, Papers, Wikipedia, Theses, Journals, Books, and Varies Annual Reports, etc.

Review of Literature

- Jaishankar N., B.S. Janagoudar, Basavaraj Kalmathh,

Vasudev Palthe Naik, and Siddayya S (2014) ^[5] Integrated Farming for Sustainable Agriculture and Livelihood Security to Rural Poor The integrated farming strategy is compared to traditional agricultural farming practices in this article. Forty hectares of land in Belagera village, Yadgir local RSK, Karnataka, were chosen for an experimental project involving twenty-five small and marginal farmers. The first research was conducted to investigate farming practices and conventional farming economics, with data collected, analyzed, and essential inputs supplied based on the Integrated farming strategy to improve agricultural farming practices. The workshop was offered to increase awareness of the advantages of integrated agricultural practices and the best use of locally available resources. Using farmers' best practices and the integrated farming approach, the crop equivalent yield (q/ha), net returns (Rs/ha), and Benefit: Cost ratio were calculated.

- Suhas P. Wani, K.H. Anantha and Kaushal K. Garg (2017) ^[4] Soil Properties, Crop Yield, and Economics Under Integrated Crop Management Practices in Karnataka Given the importance of sustainable production practices that maximize resource efficiency, a study was conducted in Karnataka, India, from 2009 to 2012 to better understand how integrated crop management (ICM) practices affected soil properties, crop yield, and economics under the Bhoochetana (soil rejuvenation) program.
- Vinodakumar S Naik (2013) ^[6] Integrated farming system for livelihood security of small farmers of North

East Karnataka In this article, the author investigated a sustainable mixed farming model that is economically viable by integrating different components such as crops, livestock, poultry, rabbits, and fish on a 2.5-acre landholding at the Main Agricultural Research Station (MARS), Raichur district of Karnataka during 2012-14. Seven integrated agricultural system models were created in order to determine the optimal package for a 2.5-acre land holding in the North-East Karnataka area. Among the different IFS models, the F7 model produced the highest net returns (Rs. 1,89,069 ha/year) and the lowest (Rs. 74,592 ha/year) in the conventional cotton alone (F1) system. The trend in return per day, diversity index, and employment creation (Rs. 518/day, 2.92, and 206 man-days/ha/year) was comparable.

- Haripriya Holachi1, Harsha Tandoti Sathyanarayanarao, Raghu Ram Achar, Vadiraj Kalya Tulasidas (2023) ^[2] A Sustainable Way for Integrated Farming System: A Case Study on Bellary District of Karnataka, India explore that in this article Because integrated crop and livestock systems have been a cornerstone of agriculture for hundreds of years, they suggest a varied variety of integrated ecological, biophysical, and socioeconomic variables. In arid locations like Bellary, it might be challenging to maintain sustainable agriculture. Adopting an effective integrated agricultural system model is critical for achieving sustainability in lowland rice farming in Karnataka's Tungabhadra project.

IFS Applications

Source: GK Today, GK Current Affairs and General Studies

- IFS promotes output per unit area through agricultural and related economic improvement.
- The integration of multiple industrial systems provides us with the opportunity to address our country's nutritional problems.
- Crop rotation, cover crops, and organic compost improve soil fertility and physical structure. It also cuts down on nutrient losses.
- It removes weeds, insect pests, and diseases through crop rotation.
- The net returns on land and labor resources are larger for the agricultural family.
- The accompanying activities in integrated farming, such as eggs, milk, mushrooms, vegetables, honey, and silkworm cocoons, also provide a constant source of money.
- It reduces component production costs by recycling input from waste of related enterprises.
- Recycling rubbish for manufacturing helps to reduce waste accumulation and contamination.
- The term "Integrated Farming System" (IFS) refers to a group of interconnected, linked, and typically interlocking production systems based on a small number of crops, animals, and associated subsidiary industries.
- They are designed primarily to maximize nutrient utilization in each system while minimizing the negative environmental repercussions of these activities.
- Because IFS is interconnected, interdependent, and interlocking, the primary and secondary outputs of one system are utilized as the major input for the other, combining the two systems into a cohesive whole.
- It entails combining agricultural activities such as cropping systems, animal husbandry, fisheries, and forestry in order to maximize resource utilization and farmer wealth.
- The components of a farming system should be selected and executed based on the availability of land, the kind of land, water, money, resources, the farmer's technical skills, market facilities, and so on.
- Integrated agricultural approaches have long been recognized as a reliable strategy for integrating the management of land, water, plants, livestock, and people.
- Integrated Farming System aims
 - We are raising the output of all component companies in order to provide more consistent and predictable income.
 - Rejuvenation/improvement of system productivity and agroecological equilibrium.
 - Maintain a low degree of intensity while adopting natural cropping system management to limit the population of insects, pests, diseases, and weeds.
 - Reducing the use of chemical fertilizer and other hazardous agrochemicals and pesticides in order to provide society with pollution-free, healthy food, and environment.

Objectives

1. To understand the applications of integrated farming in the Indian agricultural sector.
2. To examine the integrated farming structural system.

Integrated methods for agriculture in India

- To locate ecologically and financially viable enterprises in varied locations in the face of climate change.
- Using a systems approach to resource budgeting, with an emphasis on soil, water, nutrients, and energy.
- To evaluate the low-carbon production modules of the system.
- To identify and evaluate secondary agricultural solutions for recruiting rural adolescents from the

perspective of farming systems. Sustainable resource management for climate-smart IFS was implemented through station experimentation under the All Indian Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Integrated Farming Systems (IFS) beginning in 2017-18 with revised objectives, across different agro-climatic zones, and continuing through the reporting period of 2019-20, which are as follows:

Table 1: The year 2017-18 is one of new beginnings Location

Agro-climatic region	Locations (State)	Number of IFS
Western Himalaya	Chatha (J&K), Palampur (HP), Pantnagar (UK)	3
Eastern Himalaya	Umiam (Meghalaya), Jorhat (Assam)	2
Trans Gangetic Plains	Hisar (Haryana), Ludhiana (Punjab)	2
Upper Gangetic Plains	Modipuram (UP), Kanpur (UP)	2
Middle Gangetic Plains	Varanasi (UP), Faizabad (UP), Patna (Bihar), Sabour	5
Lower Gangetic Plains	(Bihar)	1
Eastern Plateau and Hills	Raipur (Chhattisgarh) Ranchi (Jharkhand)	2
Central Plateau and Hills	Jabalpur (MP)	1
Western Plateau and Hills	Akola (MS), Parbhani (MS), Rahuri (Maharashtra)	3
Southern Plateau and Hills	Rajenderanagar (Telangana), Coimbatore (TN),	5
East Coast Plains and Hills	Kathalgere (Karnataka), Sriguppa (Karnataka) Thanjavur	1
West Coast Plains and Hills	(TN)	7
Western dry	Durgapura (Rajasthan), Kota (Rajasthan)	2
Gujarat Plains and Hills	SK Nagar (Gujarat)	1
Islands	Portblair (A&N)	2
Total		39

Source: Indian Institute of Farming System Research Annual Report 2019-20

This chart lists several agro-climatic areas in India, along with their corresponding locations (states) and the number of Indian Forest Service (IFS) stations in each region. Here is an examination of the data. The table depicts the distribution of IFS stations across major agro-climatic zones in India. These stations are deliberately situated to manage and maintain forest resources in a variety of climates and habitats. Regional Focus: The location of IFS stations reflects India's emphasis on varied ecological zones, which range from the Himalayas to coastal plains and hills, as well as arid regions such as the Western arid and Western Plateau and Hills. Concentration: Certain locations have a larger concentration of IFS stations than others. For example, the West Coast Plains and Hills region contains the most stations (7), suggesting its ecological importance and probably more forest cover. Regional disparities: The number of IFS stations varies by location. For example, the Southern Plateau and Hills contain 5 stations, whereas the Central Plateau and Hills only have one, indicating probable differences in forest management focus or biological value. Strategic Locations: The location of stations appears to have been carefully designed to span a wide range of ecological conditions and biodiversity hotspots throughout India, guaranteeing successful forest management and conservation. Importance of Bihar and Tamil Nadu: Bihar and Tamil Nadu, with their numerous areas listed, appear to be critical in terms of forest management since they have a large number of IFS stations scattered over various agro-climatic zones within the states. Overall, this chart demonstrates the Indian Forest Service's complete strategy for managing and conserving India's rich biodiversity and forest resources, which includes the establishment of stations in diverse agro-climatic areas.

Western Himalayan Region

In this Agro Climatic Region, three on-station Integrated Farming Systems (IFS) models, namely Jammu (J&K), Palampur (Himachal Pradesh), and Pantnagar (Uttarakhand), were launched in 2017 to develop climate-smart IFS. The findings acquired from these IFS models for the reporting period of 2019-20 indicated a mean gross revenue of Rs. 527145. The average net return excluding household labour was shown to be Rs.429114. When family labor was factored into the cost, the mean net return from IFS models with a mean area of 1.0 ha was determined to be Rs. 394389. Table 7.1.1 shows the details of the IFS model components and cost, which showed that the average total cost for the IFS models was Rs. 250864, ranging from Rs 169519 in Palampur to Rs 338839 in Jammu Details about the IFS model, as well as the overall cost per model in WH The models were determined to be carbon negative in terms of GHG emission at -6603 CO₂ equivalent, with a mean employment creation of 457 man-days generated by different modules. Furthermore, a cost-fraction analysis found that recycled inputs accounted for around 39% of the entire cost of the IFS, while outside purchases accounted for 23% of the cost. The cost of hired labor was 14% of the total. These models demonstrated a mean REY of 24.9 tonnes and a 21.19% improvement in soil health and organic carbon over the benchmark, with net returns per rupee invested of 1.25.

The Eastern Himalayan Region

Two AICRP-IFS centers, Umiam (Meghalaya) and Jorhat (Assam) are located in this Agro Climatic Region, and climate-smart IFS model studies were launched in 2017. The findings of these IFS models acquired for the reporting

period of 2019-20 indicated a mean gross income of Rs. 563530 and a mean net return excluding family labor of Rs. 458806. When family labor was included, the average net return was determined to be Rs. 395864. Two AICRP-IFS centers, Umiam (Meghalaya) and Jorhat (Assam), are located in this Agro Climatic Region, and climate-smart IFS model studies were launched in 2017. The findings of these IFS models acquired for the reporting period of 2019-20 indicated a mean gross income of Rs. 563530 and a mean net return excluding family labor of Rs. 458806. When family labor was included, the average net return was determined to be Rs. 395864. In HER, you can find information on the IFS model as well as the overall cost per model through various modules, the models could create an average of 462 man-days of employment. Furthermore, the research of different cost fractions indicated a 2% share of recycled inputs in the overall cost of the IFS, which could be improved further, but the cost of outside acquisition was 40% of the cost. The cost of hired labor was 24% of the total. These models demonstrated a mean REY of 29.1 tonnes and a 22.7% improvement in soil health and organic carbon over the benchmark, with net returns per rupee invested of 1.20. For these models, the mean sustainable value index (SVI) was determined to be 0.7.

Region of The Middle Gangetic Plains

Since 2017, four AICRP-IFS Centres, two in Uttar Pradesh (i) IAS, BHU, Varanasi and NDUAT, Kumarganj-Faizabad, and two in Bihar (i) ICAR Research Complex for the Eastern Region, Patna., and BAU, Sabour-Bhagalpur (Bihar), have been tasked with developing climate-smart IFS Models with revised objectives for respective states. The importance of the IFS method to productivity, profitability, and livelihood of small landholders in the areas was revealed by the study's findings in 2019-20. Table 7.1.5 contains information on the various components of IFS. The findings indicated a mean gross income of Rs. 523862 and a mean net return excluding household labor of Rs. 447886. When family labor was factored into the cost, the average net return was determined to be Rs. 381286. The details of IFS model cost components shown in Table 7.1.5 revealed that the mean total cost for the IFS models was Rs. 282126, ranging from Rs 134930 in Patna (0.4 ha model) to Rs 472785 in Varanasi for 1.0 ha IFS model. Details about the IFS model, as well as the overall cost per model in MG The models, could provide a mean employment creation of 449 man-days through various modules, while the IFS models were found to be carbon negative in terms of mean GHG emission at -1146.5 CO₂ equivalent. Furthermore, a cost-fractional analysis found that recycled inputs, excluding family labor, accounted for around 30% of the overall cost of the IFS, while outside purchases, excluding labor, accounted for 30%. The cost of contracted labor was 23% of the whole cost, whereas family labor was 20% of the total cost. These models demonstrated a mean REY of 28.7 tonnes and a 12.8% improvement in soil health and organic carbon over the benchmark, with net returns per rupee invested of 1.0 and a mean SVI of 0.8.

Earth's Eastern Plateau and Hills

The two AICRP-IFS centers representing the Eastern Plateau and Hills Region, IGKV in Raipur (Chhattisgarh)

and BAU in Kanke Ranchi (Jharkhand), were assessed for the creation of climate-smart IFS models for the livelihood enhancement of the region's small and marginal farmers. The IFS model was stretched across 1.0 hectares in both sites. During the reporting year of 2019-20, the findings of IFS models from these centers indicated a mean gross income of Rs. 408297 and a mean net return excluding labor of Rs.373826. Details of IFS model components and costs are shown in Table 7.1.7, which shows that the average total cost for IFS models was Rs. 202025, ranging from Rs 179083 in Ranchi to Rs 224967 in Raipur for 1.0 ha IFS models Details about the IFS model, as well as the overall cost per model in EPH

SPH (Southern Plateau and Hills)

Four AICRP-IFS centers are placed in distinct NARP zones of the country's Southern Plateau and Hill ACZ: TNAU, Coimbatore (Tamilnadu), ARS, Kathalgere (Karnataka), ANGRAU, Rajendra Nagar, Hyderabad (A.P.), and ARS, Sirriguppa (Karnataka). In addition, a new sub-center is being constructed in Maruteru, A.P. The findings of the study conducted at these centers during 2019-20, together with IFS components, are provided in Table 7.1.10, revealing a mean gross income of Rs. 406707 and a mean net return excluding family labor of Rs.329337. When family labor was factored into the cost, the average net return was determined to be Rs. 282435. Details of IFS model cost components shown in Table 7.1.10 revealed that the mean total cost for the IFS models was Rs. 264426, ranging from Rs 161523 at the Kathalgere model to Rs 414828 at the Coimbatore model for 1.0 ha IFS model. Details about the IFS model, as well as the overall cost per model in SPH Through various modules, the models could provide a mean employment generation of 504 man-days, while the IFS models were shown to be carbon negative in terms of mean GHG emission at -3958 CO₂ equivalent. Furthermore, a cost-fraction analysis found that recycled inputs accounted for around 25% of the entire cost of the IFS, while outside purchases accounted for 29%. Hiring labor cost 18% of the total cost. These models demonstrated a mean REY of 28.2 tonnes, as well as a 42.2% improvement in soil health and organic carbon improvement over the benchmark, with net returns per rupee invested of 1.6 and a mean SVI of 0.71.a

Suggestions and Finding

- The area under cultivation shrinks
- Holding is small and fragmented.
- Seasonality of income, employment, and out-migration
- Depletion of the resource basis
- Household necessities

Conclusion

The integration of fish with cattle and agriculture must be considered since this activity may significantly improve rural living by increasing return on investment. An integrated farming system appears to be the solution to the challenges of boosting food production, increasing income, and improving the nutrition of small-scale farmers with limited resources while minimizing environmental and agroecosystem impacts. IFS is a potential technique for enhancing overall productivity and profitability by reusing

agricultural byproducts and utilizing available resources more efficiently. It has the potential to create additional job possibilities for rural communities all year long, as well as improve economic and nutritional security.

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